

YOUTH ASSEMBLY IN PERSON WORKSHOPS
SEPTEMBER & OCTOBER

TESTING THE GREENSCENT CITIZEN JOURNALISM APP

FEEDBACK ON THE GREENSCENT
CITIZEN JOURNALISM APP FROM
FOUR IN-PERSON WORKSHOPS IN
THE GREENSCENT YOUTH
ASSEMBLIES

Prepared for GreenSCENT by Sif Juhl Jacobsen and Ida Skov
Nielsen, Project Managers at The Danish Board of Technology

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INTRODUCTION

This report provides insights into young individuals' experiences engaging with the GreenSCENT Citizen Journalism app. The report presents their experience testing the app and provides comprehensive feedback from the Youth Assemblies to the app's engineering team.

What is The GreenSCENT journalism app?

With the GreenSCENT citizen journalism platform, users will be able to collect information, monitor and report environmental issues or solutions about a specific area or territory.

BACKGROUND: THE YOUTH ASSEMBLIES

Uniting 56 Participants from Seven European Nations in Collaborative Workshops

The GreenSCENT Youth Assemblies convened in in-person meetings on four weekends in September and October 2023. Each Youth Assembly traveled to a European city (Copenhagen, Barcelona, Rome and Novi Sad), where they spend the weekend working in depth with the GreenSCENT content. One of the main workshops during the four weekends was the GreenSCENT Citizen Journalism app workshop. Here the participants were introduced to the app, and got to test it in a case setting over a day or a half day, within the focus of a specific Green Deal Competence Area. Afterwards, the participants gave their feedback on the app during a specific feedback workshop hosted by The Danish Board of Technology (DBT). This report communicates the feedback from that workshop.

First time reading about the Youth Assemblies?

The Youth Assemblies have already helped co-creating the GreenSCENT Citizen Journalism App prior to testing the application on the in-person meetings.

The Youth Assemblies are divided into four assemblies with a total of 56 young people (14 in each), with participants aged between 14 and 24 from seven European countries – Denmark, Finland, Greece, Italy, Romania, Serbia, and Spain. Since September 2022, these dedicated young people have convened and participated in online workshops facilitated by GreenSCENT project managers and partners every other month to discuss a wide variety of important topics that are central to the state of our planet and society. The young participants test apps and tools under development, provide feedback, and generate ideas and suggestions for the design and implementation of these tools in educational settings. DBT designs and facilitates the activities of the Youth Assemblies.

THE FEEDBACK PROCESS

TESTING OF THE GREENSCENT APP

Previous to the feedback workshops, the Youth Assemblies had, guided by DBT, and supported by ENG, been testing the app in a case setting in the European city, where the specific in person meeting was hosted. In Copenhagen, 12 participants worked with the Green Deal Competence Area Clean Air and tested the GreenSCENT app by visiting and posting about different institutions contributing to the energy transition. In Barcelona, 14 participants worked with the Green Deal Competence Area Zero Pollution and tested the GreenSCENT app by documenting their work, putting up air test tubes using the CleanAir@Schools app, developed by 4sfera, on a long walk around the city center in Barcelona. In Rome, 14 participants worked with the Green Deal Competence Area From Farm to Fork, and tested the GreenSCENT app in a local farmer's market, identifying food produce with various climate footprints and documenting their investigation through the GreenSCENT app. And in Novi Sad, 11 participants worked with the Green Deal Competence Area Circular Economy, testing the GreenSCENT app by testing the GreenSCENT app by posting reports about their experiences with circular economy in the city.

THE GREENSCENT APP FEEDBACK WORKSHOP

Before travelling home from the four in-person meetings, DBT hosted a local Feedback Workshop for each Youth Assembly, where the participants were asked to provide feedback on experience with the GreenSCENT app during the weekend. Four feedback workshops were convened (one in each city), each with around 14 participants. The feedback design, which was developed by DBT and shared with ENG on beforehand, was the same in each of the four workshops, with few exceptions. DBT hosted all four workshops.

The participants were asked to, individually or in small groups, rate and elaborate on their experience with the app. First by focusing on their experience with downloading and accessing the app. And secondly by focusing on their experience with using and navigating in the app. The participants were also asked to elaborate specifically on their opinions on the categories / tags in the app ("Risk", "Pollution", "Emergency" and "Solution". Next, they were asked to assess whether the app would be useful in a school setting. And lastly, the participants were asked to share any additional comments and reflections that they might have about the app. This part of the exercise was done individually and not in groups.

“

THE APP WILL BE EFFECTIVE WHEN
GOING ON AN EXCURSION TO LEARN
MORE ABOUT THE AREA AS WELL AS
GET INTRODUCED TO NEW SOLUTIONS.

”

METHOD OF ANALYZING THE DATA

The data from the four Feedback Workshops have been pooled and analyzed together. The feedback report can be found in the appendix. Recurrent or similar statements have been pooled and incorporated into one single statement containing the relevant information. Any statement or opinion which has been mentioned a substantial number of times (in general more than five times), has been marked with a parenthesis, explaining that a significant number of participants agreed on this, sometimes followed by an elaboration. This pooling method is used in the entire report, except in the last chapter, where the participants individually share their additional comments and reflections.

In the first part of the feedback report, the feedback from the four Youth Assemblies has been summarized, and the most repeated statements have been broken down into suitable categories.

SUMMARY OF THE FEEDBACK

On the following pages you can read the statements, which were repeated most during the four workshops. The full combined feedback report with all statements, reflections, and ratings from the four feedback workshops can be found in the appendix.

FEEDBACK ON DOWNLOADING AND ACCESSING THE APP

Most participants appreciated these features and functions:

- The app is intuitive and has a visually appealing design.
- All functions in the app worked, including posting text, photos, and videos.
- The app was easy to download by following the given instructions (though it would be even easier if the app was available in Google Play / Appstore.)

Most participants found that these features and functions have problems to be addressed:

- The app should be available in Google Play / Appstore, as download and access instructions were not clear.
- There were difficulties getting the app to work / getting access. The issues included: Needing to register several times in order to sign in, inability to or difficulties in validating e-mail address, inability for some iPhone users to access the app because it kept asking for location service, even if it was already turned on, no way to recover password, getting logged out of the app without obvious reason followed by screen turning white.
- The app should not require having access to GPS in order to work / The GPS usage should be limited. Some experienced that the “New” button in the app only worked when the location service was turned on. Some iPhone users were not able to access the app, because it kept asking for location service, even if it was already turned on. Some had trouble allowing access to location service on their iPhone.

FEEDBACK ON USING AND NAVIGATING IN THE APP

Most participants appreciated these features and functions:

- The map feature where you can see posts from all over the world was very useful, though it could be improved with search functions and a satellite mode.
- The tags/categories were relevant and offered a useful way to categorize and sort the type of post you are making/searching for, though the categories should be expanded, or it should be possible to make your own categories/tags.
- The possibility to add photos/media is very useful when picturing risks in your own minds. The upload function could be improved, however, to allow multiple uploads better video quality and faster upload. There could also be improvements in relation to text post, so they could be more blog like, i.e. more characters allowed and the possibility to comment and react on each other's posts.

Most participants found that these features and functions have problems to be addressed:

- There were difficulties in being allowed to post. Various troubleshooting was tried, but not all succeeded in fixing the problem(s). The issues included: Inability to post photos from their account, the placement of the four categories in the bottom of the page is not working with iPhone, as it overlaps, quality loss when uploading videos, video upload does not work well, as it keeps refreshing or loading, app closing down on its own without saving your text.
- The login page / front page could be more intuitive and clear. I.e. change the sideways scroll to top down scroll, Download and access instructions were not clear. There could be a tutorial on the very first page on how to download, register, sign in, add to home screen, turn on location service, post photos, videos, text etc. And there could be a little mascot guiding you as you move on into the app. Some suggested to have a homepage or feed where you could see others' posts and interact with them to make it more engaging. I.e. search for your own city or friends, and comment on and like/dislike other people's posts.
- The app shouldn't require approval from administrators in order for you to make a post. As it is now, posts in the app need approval every time.

**A SPECIAL THANKS TO ALL PARTICIPANTS IN THE
GREENSCENT YOUTH ASSEMBLIES FOR ENGAGING
IN DEVELOPING IDEAS AND SHARING REFLECTIONS
AND INSIGHTS ON THE GREEN APPS.**

APPENDIX

In addition to this report, you can read the full combined feedback report with all statements, reflections and ratings from the four feedback workshops below.

Appendix: Feedback on the GreenSCENT app

This document is the full combined feedback report with all statements, reflections, and ratings from the four feedback workshops. In the following chapters (except in the last chapter on individual opinions and reflections) similar statements have been pooled, in order to decrease complexity.

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Downloading and accessing the app

Individual rating of overall experience with downloading the app

Rating	1 (worst)	2	3	4	5 (best)
Number of people agreeing	10	18	16	8	1

Participants mentioned the following reasons that their overall experience with downloading and accessing the app went well:

- The app was easy to download by following the given instructions. *(A significant number of people agreed on this, followed by a note that it would be even easier if the app was available in Appstore/Google Play.)*
- The app has a visually appealing and engaging design. *(A significant number of people agreed on this)*
- The app has good features.
- The app is intuitive and easy to understand. *(A significant number of people agreed on this)*
- The app worked well on Android phones.
- It was easy to register and log into the app.
- All functions in the app worked, including posting text, photos and videos. *(A significant number of people agreed on this)*

Participants encountered the following problems and issues related to downloading and accessing the app. Some of the issues are followed by the participants' suggestions for improvement:

- There were difficulties getting the app to work / getting access. Some did not succeed to get the app to work at all. Some needed to register again, in order to be able to sign in. *(A significant number of people had trouble getting the app to work / getting access)*
- Registration in the app requires approval by administrator. It would be useful and save a lot of time if the users could confirm their identity themselves. The app should tell you the reason that you are not allowed to post, so you can fix it. I.e. by waiting for approval from the administrators. *(A significant number of people agreed that the app shouldn't require approval from administrators in order for you to make a post.)*
- It was not intuitive, that you need to scroll sideways to see different departments. It should be a scroll down / drop down menu instead. DBT's department was the very last one, when scrolling sideways, which made it hard to find.

- Download and access instructions were not clear. There could be a tutorial on the very first page on how to download, register, sign in, add to home screen, turn on location service, post photos, videos, text etc. And there could be a little mascot guiding you as you move on into the app. A feed in chronological order would be good. It would also help a lot, if the app was available for download in Google Play / AppStore. *(A significant number of people agreed that it should be easier to download and access, and a significant number of people agreed that it should be possible to download the app in Google Play / AppStore.)*
- Validating e-mail address feels sketchy for several reasons: It is only in Italian and the page is “not found” when validating. Some did not succeed in validating their e-mail address.
- The app should not require to have access to GPS in order to work / The GPS usage should be limited. Some experienced that the “New” button in the app only worked when the location service was turned on. Some iPhone users was not able to access the app, because it kept asking for location service, even if it was already turned on. Some has trouble allowing access to location service on their iPhone. *(A significant number of people agreed that the requirement of location service was a problem.)*
- It should be possible to use other browsers than Google Chrome.
- It should be possible to recover your password. *(A significant number of people agreed on this)*

Participants had the following further comments related to downloading and accessing the app:

- I keep getting logged out of the app and when I try opening it again, the screen turns white and I have to reinstall the app and redo the login process.

Using and navigating in the app

Individual rating of overall experience with using and navigating in the app

Rating	1	2	3	4	5
Number of people	3	9	15	10	0

Participants found the following elements and possibilities in the app particularly well-functioning or interesting to use:

- The map feature where you can see posts from all over the world and add whatever you want. *(A significant number of people agreed on this)*
- Tags with texts and photos are aesthetically pleasing and interesting.
- The possibility to add photos/media is very useful when picturing risks in your own minds. *(A significant number of people agreed on this)*

Participants encountered the following problems and issues related to using and navigating in the app. Some of the issues are followed by the participants' suggestions for improvement:

- Several users could not post photos from their account. Some solved the problem by logging in and out many times. Some tried solving the problem by switching between using the app and using Google Chrome, logging in and out, and disabling and enabling location service, but without success. *(A significant number of people agreed on this)*
- Posts in the app needed approval every time.
- The login page / front page could be more intuitive and clear. *(A significant number of people agreed on this)*
- The app is slow.
- The app requires too much supervision / guidance.
- "Close" and "Menu" is the same button as "Home button" on Apple Phones, which causes a problem if you press the button.
- The app is not compatible with navigation apps which are not Chrome.
- The "choose region" was confusing.
- When you go back with the home button, it takes you to the start instead of to the list of posts.
- The placement of the four categories in the bottom of the page is not working with iPhone, as it overlaps.
- The workflow option on posts is unnecessary for the user.

- The app could be more professional and engaging if its appearance was improved and it was more fun to use. I.e., some of the buttons are not intuitive (for example “close”). There are also a few spelling mistakes and many bugs, i.e. app closing down on its own and doesn’t save your texts, inability to make a new post, etc.)
- There is a huge quality loss when uploading videos. And the video upload does not work well, as it keeps refreshing or loading.

Besides the suggestions mentioned already, the participants had the following suggestions for improvement in the app, related to using and navigating in the app:

- It should be possible to see posts from all countries.
- There should be a section where you can discuss green issues.
- Photos, text and videos should be unlimited in posts, also allowing for editing after you have posted. Upload of multiple photos at the same time should be possible.
- Shortened words should be explained.
- It should be possible to filtrate by the type of post, so that you can go straight to the type of post you want to see.
- It should be easier to use the map when making posts – i.e. a search feature for addresses and places. There could also be a satellite option and a search function in the map. And why do I see posts risks in Denmark while being in Serbia? *(A significant number of people agreed that the map features could be improved.)*
- There should be a search/find function.
- It would be nice to have a homepage or feed where you could see others’ posts and interact with them to make it more engaging. I.e. search for your own city or friends, and comment on and like/dislike other people’s posts. *(A significant number of people agreed that interaction with others could be improved.)*
- It should be possible to copy+paste.
- There could be categories of blog posts, reports, opinions, discussions, including the option to change font and style.
- There should be an option to upload a profile picture.
- Support function should be added.
- It could be more interesting with games and other activities, and by providing more functions and involving more countries

Participants mentioned the following experiences with the categories “Risk”, “Pollution”, “Emergency” and “Solutions”. Some of the statements are followed by the participants’ suggestions for improvement:

- It was not obvious that the categories should be chosen, as they didn’t look like buttons. They could perhaps have another color. *(A significant number of people agreed on this)*
- The categories should have a description, to make it more clear why they were relevant. It was not obvious what they should be used for.
- The categories were relevant and offered a useful way to categorize and sort the type of post you are making / searching for. *(A significant number of people agreed on this)*

- The categories give a fun, “modern touch” to the app, like a social media app. *(A significant number of people agreed on this)*
- The category ratings need more options than just low to high. I.e. weak to strong. It would be useful to classify the type of problem, i.e. related to water, air, etc. Subcategories could also be an option. It would also be useful to know whether some places are safe. *(A significant number of people agreed that the category options are too limited.)*
- An option to “rate this situation” should be added.
- The categories are too strict / closed.
- It should be possible to add your own category / hashtag. *(A significant number of people agreed on this)*
- “Pollution” did not quite fit in with the other tags/categories. The category could be more clear on the main page.
- The hashtag is not necessary, but the categories are good for rating the post.

Using the app in school/education

Which of the following statements best describes your opinion?

Statements	Number of agreeing participants	Comments
Using the app in school will make me feel empowered to act and contribute to the green transition (by making content).	11	N/A
Using the app in school would make learning more interesting and involving.	32	<p>When you've reached high school or higher more advanced info and features to still make it academically relevant.</p> <p>I think for primary students/younger people, it's more beneficial in wanting to learn more. It is an interesting way to learn stuff & a fun, interactive way.</p> <p>It could be more interesting and involving in primary (young people) school, since it might be a more visual and interactive way of learning.</p> <p>It would be effective when going on an excursion to learn more about the area as well as get introduced to new solutions.</p> <p>I think it can be an interesting tool to learn about the environmental situation in other regions/countries as an alternative 'social media'.</p>
Using the app in school wouldn't make learning more interesting.	9	<p>How would it?</p> <p>I don't think so, because during a university degree, you don't really have time to make posts, it will only distract you.</p> <p>Not in the case of a university level degree, because students might be mature enough to aim for different motivations.</p> <p>I think it's not an easy app to use, and not really interesting for young people.</p>

Overall opinions and reflections on the app

The following statements have not been pooled together. Each statement represents a single response.

Participants elaborated on their individual opinions and reflections on the app:

- It will be something new to the students, and also, they don't have to carry anything extra. It could be a fun experience.
- The app allows for content to be made which made me feel like I'm contributing by uploading something which would be useful in schools. The usability of the app and how it's visibly laid out plus the fact that we had a few problems using it may make learning a little boring. However, if this app allowed for school trips in the city, it would make learning about the green transition interesting and fun.
- Student can post about what they care about, but I hope the app needs to be always supervised by an adult so every post can be controlled and make a good use of it.
- I believe students would be excited to try the app. The idea is good, but it could be more engaging – could it maybe be more like a game?
- I think using the app is a fun way to engage students in learning and sharing their thoughts. Moreover, it's intuitive and easy to use. It is definitely an improvement for schools.
- The app is a fun and engaging way to talk about durability and climate change. Should be introduced by teacher on beforehand.
- Using the app in school would be very interesting and useful, but for some students this app will be boring because it's not exactly something they would be interested in.
- I really like the idea of the 360 view. It's a nice app and I believe young children would like to use it.
- Using this app in school would help children raise awareness of importance of pollution and the way it affects the globe.
- It would make the lesson more interesting, but I would add more functions for all to find it interesting
- The app could be made more similar to current popular platforms like Reddit.
- The app would help people to learn about important/not so important matters that they would like to know.
- At the moment the app doesn't seem useful for high-school and university level students.
- Small research questions & works of students can be used and published instead of just grading and done.
- The app contributes to spread democracy even more.
- Students will be more aware about where they live and take action in their own hands and make change.
- Expressing creativity though writing can be beneficial for students to be future researchers.

- Possibility to hear the voice of youth and to educate them about these matters shows great opportunity. Only issue is that posts cannot be updated.
- The app can make kids be more aware of their surroundings and environment.
- Learning would be more engaging in a way where you produce a product that also doesn't always have to follow proper essay structure.
- I think it's a fun way to learn, it is not the "traditional" way, and students can actively participate and share their opinions and thoughts.
- It's an uninteresting app - I don't find it inspiring, but it's a bit chaotic.
- Does it have other uses aside from learning? Could you use it if you work with environmental problems?
- It reminds me of Environmental Justice Atlas.
- I don't know if I will use it in my daily life. But probably if I go on a vacation to another European city, I would use it to know more about the city I am visiting.
- I don't really understand practical use of the app, right now I don't feel like I will need it anytime/anywhere except these meetings.
- It's a good concept but I also don't think I'll remember to post stuff I see. I think it will be difficult to get people to do this in their free time.